

PARASITOLOGICAL SCIENCES

APPLICATION OF REAL-TIME PCR AND KATO-KATZ METHODS IN MONITORING THE TREATMENT EFFICACY OF *TRICHURIS TRICHIURA* INFECTIONS

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Abstract

Trichuris trichiura is a geohelminth infection that affects approximately 460 million people worldwide, making it the second most common after *Ascaris lumbricoides*. The Kato-Katz (KK) method, endorsed by the World Health Organization (WHO), remains a widely used diagnostic technique. In a clinical trial, the KK method was compared with the real-time polymerase chain reaction (PCR) method to evaluate the efficacy of treatment with albendazole and ivermectin.

The study, conducted on 84 participants, revealed a diagnostic concordance rate of 88.7% between the two methods in detecting *Trichuris trichiura* eggs. Real-time PCR demonstrated higher sensitivity, especially in low-intensity infections, indicating that the KK method may not be optimal in such cases. PCR showed superiority in assessing treatment efficacy and could be considered among the preferred diagnostic methods in broader applications.

The study also compared the effectiveness of combination therapy with albendazole and ivermectin in children aged 2–14 years, using various treatment regimens. Examinations conducted before and after treatment using both KK and PCR methods showed a reduction in the number of infected individuals. In conclusion, the application of real-time PCR provides a more accurate diagnosis of *Trichuris trichiura* and a better evaluation of treatment efficacy. The study further emphasizes the need for developing precise parameters for the future diagnostic application of molecular techniques.

Keywords: *Trichuris trichiura*, Kato-Katz method, real-time polymerase chain reaction method, epidemiological study, albendazole/ivermectin combination.

Introduction.

Trichuris trichiura is a geohelminth infection that affects approximately 460 million people worldwide and is the second most common helminth infection in humans after *Ascaris lumbricoides* (1). The disease is transmitted through the ingestion of contaminated food or water sources. The Kato-Katz (KK) method is still recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO) as a standard diagnostic technique; however, its sensitivity may be insufficient in cases of low-intensity infections (2).

Objective:

The aim of the study is to compare the efficacy of combination therapy with albendazole and ivermectin using the Kato-Katz (KK) and real-time polymerase chain reaction (PCR) diagnostic methods.

Materials and Methods:

A total of 84 participants were included in the study, and the cure rate (CR) was analyzed.

The quantity of *Trichuris trichiura* eggs detected after treatment was evaluated using both methods, and the diagnostic concordance between them was found to be 88.7%. The discrepancy observed in the study is likely attributable to infections with lower intensity. The use of the PCR method was considered appropriate as an alternative for assessing the cure rate (CR). These

diagnostic approaches highlight the necessity of determining suitable diagnostic tools for clinical trials.

Trichuris trichiura, caused by the whipworm geohelminth, is targeted by the World Health Organization (WHO) through periodic treatment with benzimidazole drugs in endemic regions. It has been determined that one of the main challenges in monitoring and evaluating treatment efficacy is the need for highly sensitive and effective diagnostic methods. In some epidemiological studies, multiplex real-time PCR has been used for diagnosing *Trichuris trichiura*; however, its application in clinical trials remains limited due to the small number of such studies. The findings suggest that real-time PCR could become one of the widely used diagnostic methods, but the development of standardized guidelines is essential for its broader implementation.

The Kato-Katz (KK) method is recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO) and is used for clinical diagnosis in epidemiological studies. However, the sensitivity of the KK method is not optimal, particularly in areas with low-intensity infections [1]. As the prevalence and intensity of geohelminth infections decline [12], both microscopy-based and more sensitive DNA-based diagnostic techniques have been investigated [11]. The latter have been especially proposed to complement existing programmatic standards [3, 4].

Real-time PCR molecular techniques have been tested in terms of sensitivity, specificity, and diagnostic performance [9]. Indeed, real-time PCR has demonstrated higher sensitivity compared to microscopy-based examinations [8]. Unfortunately, only a limited number of studies have been conducted in this area, and these have been evaluated primarily in the context of clinical trials assessing the efficacy of treatment regimens for geohelminth infections [2, 5].

In this review, the Kato-Katz (KK) and real-time PCR methods were compared to evaluate the efficacy of albendazole and ivermectin combination therapy in the treatment of *Trichuris trichiura*. In the context of clinical trials, the reduction in helminth egg count, helminth elimination (cure), or the decrease in the intensity of the infection were considered as key indicators.

The study included children aged 2–14 years, weighing >15 kg, diagnosed with *Trichuris trichiura*. They were divided into four treatment groups:

- Albendazole 400 mg dose;
- Albendazole + Ivermectin (600 mg/kg single dose);
- Albendazole 400 mg for 3 days;
- Albendazole + Ivermectin (600 mg/kg) for 3 days.

This study was conducted in two villages, where it was determined that the prevalence of *Trichuris trichiura* was over 50% during the survey [6]. A total of 230 samples were analyzed using both real-time PCR and Kato-Katz methods. The examinations were carried out on 230 samples collected from 115 individuals, and the results of both methods were compared and analyzed. In 94 samples, both diagnostic methods yielded positive results. According to WHO guidelines, the examinations were repeated before and after treatment, between days 14 and 21. For the Kato-Katz method, one stool sample was collected from each participant based on the sequence of examination [10], and a smear was prepared. To count *Trichuris trichiura* eggs in the smear, the sample was examined under the microscope for 20–60 minutes. Using a template, the egg count per gram was calculated, and light, moderate, and heavy infections were determined based on the results, in accordance with WHO guidelines. For the real-time PCR method, three stool samples were collected and stored in 99% ethanol at room temperature. These samples were then washed with distilled water to remove ethanol and centrifuged. DNA was extracted using the Fast DNA Spin Kit as described by Mejra et al. [7].

Pre-designed primers specific to *Trichuris trichiura* species and a FAM-labeled minor groove binder probe targeting the ITS region of the helminth were used for real-time PCR amplification. Data analysis was performed using the Stata software.

The cure rate (CR) was determined based on the proportion of individuals who showed a positive result in the initial phase, but a negative result after treatment, for both diagnostic methods. Fisher's test was used to compare the treatment rates obtained by CR between treatment and control groups for both real-time PCR and Kato-Katz methods. Diagnostic concordance was

calculated for all samples based on the number of samples showing the same positive or negative results for both methods.

Conclusion

This study was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of treatment in clinical trials and to assess whether the PCR and Kato-Katz (KK) methods could be used interchangeably as diagnostic tools. However, insufficient data was obtained to establish a correlation between the cycle threshold (CT) in PCR and the egg count per gram (EPG) determined by KK. As a result, it was not possible to evaluate real-time PCR as a quantitative diagnostic method.

The results indicate that although the Kato-Katz method is still used in diagnostics, its sensitivity is not optimal in low-intensity infections. The application of real-time PCR has provided a significant advantage in the diagnosis of *Trichuris trichiura*, offering higher sensitivity. Therefore, real-time PCR can currently be considered one of the widely used methods and is a more effective diagnostic tool for evaluating the treatment efficacy of *Trichuris trichiura*.

As geohelminth control programs develop, new treatment guidelines, monitoring strategies, and other relevant issues will become critical. In this regard, rather than attempting to adapt different diagnostic methods based on microscopy, it may be more appropriate to develop new parameters for molecular methods.

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